

Physical Seed Characteristics of Clary Sage (*Salvia sclarea* L.) at Different Altitudes in Denizli

Tansu USKUTOĞLU^{1*}

¹ Pamukkale University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Field Crops, Denizli

*Corresponding author: tuskutoglu@pau.edu.tr

Abstract

This study investigates the geographic variation in the physical seed characteristics of clary sage (*Salvia sclarea* L.) collected from diverse locations within Denizli province, Türkiye. Clary sage is a commercially and medicinally significant species, widely distributed in the Mediterranean and valued for its essential oil. Despite its economic importance, there are no registered cultivars in Türkiye, highlighting the need for local breeding programs. The primary aim of this research was to determine key physical properties of clary sage seeds—specifically length, width, thickness, geometric mean diameter (Dg), sphericity (Φ), surface area (S), and thousand seed weight (TSW)—and to assess how these traits vary according to collection site. Seed samples were gathered from 15 distinct locations, and their physical attributes were measured and statistically analysed. The results revealed significant location-dependent variation in all measured traits ($p < 0.05$). Seed length ranged from 1.13 to 1.46 mm, width from 1.88 to 2.20 mm, and thickness from 1.21 to 1.49 mm. The L6 location produced the largest seeds in terms of length, width, geometric mean diameter, and surface area, while L5 seeds had the highest TSW, indicating greater endosperm content. Principal component analysis (PCA) further demonstrated that altitude negatively correlated with seed size, and a strong positive relationship existed between seed thickness and TSW. The study concludes that certain locations, particularly L1, L2, and L6, have potential for producing high-quality seeds, which is valuable for breeding and agricultural practices.

Research Article

Article History

Received :15.03.2025
Accepted :25.04.2025

Keywords

Salvia sclarea L.
clary sage
altitude
seed morphology

1. Introduction

Salvia L. is a large genus, comprising around 1000 species, and exhibits a subcosmopolitan distribution, indicating its widespread presence in diverse environments worldwide (González-Gallegos et al., 2020). In the flora of Türkiye, the genus *Salvia* is represented by 100 species and 107 taxa. Remarkably, nearly 50% of these species are endemic, indicating a significant level of endemism within the country (Karik et al., 2018; Tursun et al., 2021). The genus *Salvia* is recognized as one of the largest within the Lamiaceae family. Among its numerous species, those with the greatest commercial significance include *S. officinalis* L., *S. fruticosa* Mill. (syn. *S. triloba* L.), *S. pomifera* L., *S. lavandulaefolia* Vahl, and *S. sclarea* L. (Sharopov and Setzer, 2012; Tursun et al., 2021). *Salvia sclarea* L., widely referred to as clary sage, is an herbaceous plant that can grow as a biennial or perennial. Indigenous to the Mediterranean Basin, this species is valued for its aromatic and medicinal properties and is well-adapted to a variety of environmental conditions (Grigoriadou et al., 2020). As a result, it is widely distributed across all geographical regions of Türkiye. It is widely utilized not only in traditional medicine and culinary applications, but also in the cosmetics, fragrance, and pharmaceutical industries. Members of the *Salvia* genus are notable for a broad spectrum of biological activities, including antibacterial, antioxidant, antitumor, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, anxiolytic, sedative, and anti-inflammatory properties (Cui et al., 2015; Safaei-Ghomi et al., 2016). Clary sage is commercially cultivated on a large scale in several countries, including Russia, Bulgaria, France, and Morocco, with an estimated annual global production of approximately 150 tons of essential oil (Acimovic et al., 2022). There are no registered or officially protected cultivars of this species in Türkiye. In contrast, several registered varieties and cultivars of clary sage have been developed in countries such as France, Bulgaria, and Romania. In these countries, selection and breeding programs focused on essential oil production have led to the

development of officially recognized cultivars. Additionally, hybrid varieties have also been produced, including early-ripening, medium-ripening, and late-ripening types (Goncariuc and Balmuş, 2010). Considering Türkiye's rich plant diversity, developing local cultivars of valuable and widely distributed clary sage is of great importance. The development of local varieties that are adapted to Türkiye's different ecological regions, with high yield and high-quality essential oil content, will provide farmers with an alternative product and contribute to the local economy. In this context, not only yield and quality but also the physical properties of seeds play a significant role in the development of new varieties. The selection of high-quality cultivars adapted to local ecological conditions relies on the detailed analysis of these seed characteristics. Seed characteristics provide valuable information for agricultural practices, harvesting, and storage. Knowing these physical traits helps design better harvesting machines and prepare seeds for food processing. Accurate estimation of parameters such as shape, size, volume, density, and surface area, whether for bulk or individual units, is important for food production. Measurement techniques enable the calculation of these parameters and offer insights into the effects of processing (Dobrzański and Stepniewski, 2013). Moreover, detailed analysis of these seed characteristics plays a crucial role in plant breeding and variety selection. By evaluating physical seed traits, breeders can identify and select superior genotypes, thereby accelerating the development of improved cultivars. Research on seed characteristics of clary sage remains limited, with no comprehensive studies having been conducted at the specific collection sites where plant materials have been gathered. This knowledge gap represents a significant limitation in understanding the morphological and physiological properties of seeds from different geographical populations, which could provide valuable insights into genetic diversity, adaptation mechanisms, and potential cultivation strategies for this economically important medicinal plant

species. The aim of this study was to determine several physical properties of clary sage (*Salvia sclarea* L.) seeds, including length (mm), width (mm), thickness (mm), geometric mean diameter (D_g , mm), sphericity (Φ , %), surface area (S , mm^2), and thousand seed weight (TSW, g), and to evaluate how these parameters are influenced by different collection locations. Understanding these characteristics and their variation across locations is essential not only for optimizing harvesting, processing, and storage practices, and ensuring seed quality and efficient equipment use, but also for supporting plant breeding and variety selection efforts by providing key data on seed traits that may be associated with desirable agronomic performance.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Collection of seed samples

Denizli province and its districts constitute an important centre of diversity for clary sage distribution. Seed samples were collected from various districts throughout Denizli province. The seeds used in this study were collected during the early autumn period (September 2024), when the seed heads had fully matured and dried. Details regarding the collection sites are provided in Table 1. Areas with dense plant populations were preferred for seed collection (with more than 20 individuals per site). The amount of seeds collected ranged between 30 and 50 grams.

Table 1. Location information of clary sage seeds collected from different sites in Denizli province

Location	Description Name	Coordinate	Altitude (m)
L1	Baklan	37° 56' 42" N 29° 36' 04" E	1.205
L2	Mecidiye	37° 54' 59" N 29° 37' 32" E	1.212
L3	Cindere	38° 06' 02" N 29° 03' 57" E	711
L4	Çokaklı	38° 20' 58" N 29° 36' 44" E	906
L5	Beylerli	37° 41' 46" N 29° 38' 14" E	910
L6	Gülalan	38° 05' 37" N 28° 47' 30" E	720
L7	ÜçKuyu	38° 16' 17" N 29° 27' 43" E	947
L8	Aşağı Çeşme	38° 11' 41" N 29° 04' 44" E	749
L9	Haytabey	38° 00' 30" N 29° 07' 24" E	836
L10	Yahyalar	38° 14' 08" N 29° 23' 30" E	856
L11	Dağmarmara	38° 05' 58" N 29° 13' 55" E	599
L12	Selcen	38° 05' 06" N 29° 21' 42" E	971
L13	Bozalan	38° 06' 07" N 28° 52' 24" E	597
L14	Sakızcılar	38° 01' 04" N 29° 15' 45" E	1.023
L15	Güzelyurt	37° 10' 25" N 29° 22' 41" E	1.295

2.2. Measurement of physical and morphological properties

The seeds were allowed to dry under ambient room conditions until they reached a constant weight, after which the required measurements were performed. Seed characteristics of length (mm), width (mm), and thickness (mm) were measured using a stereomicroscope (Soif Optical Instruments,

Smart 1/L). Measurements were conducted at the Laboratory of the Faculty of Agriculture, Pamukkale University, using a calibration with millimeter paper at 10x magnification. The geometric mean diameter (D_g), sphericity, and surface area of the seeds were calculated using the dimensions measured under the microscope, according to equation 1, 2, and 3, respectively (Bayram et al., 2016; Dumanoğlu et al., 2019).

$$D_g = (\text{LWT})^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi = \left[\frac{(\text{LWT})^{\frac{1}{3}}}{L} \right] * 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S = \pi D_g^2 \quad (3)$$

The physical characteristics of the seeds were determined using 20 seeds with three replications, while the thousand seed weight (TSW) was measured using 100 seeds, also with three replications.

2.3. Statistics analysis

Seed characteristic traits were determined in a randomized plot experimental design with three replications. The data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and differences among groups were identified using the Tukey HSD multiple comparison test. Statistical significance was considered at the level of $P < 0.05$. Statistical analyses and biplot analysis were both performed using the JMP software package.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 2 presents the physical characteristics examined in clary sage seeds collected from different regions within Denizli province. The seed dimensions (length, width, thickness), shape parameters (D_g , Φ , S), and weight (TSW) values were statistically analysed. These data provide important insights into location-dependent variation in seed morphology, and statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed for all traits. Seed length ranged from 1.13 to 1.46 mm. The longest seeds (1.46 mm) were found in the L2, L3, and L6 locations, while the shortest seeds (1.13 mm) were observed in the L12 location. Seed width ranged from 1.88 to 2.20 mm. The widest seeds (2.20 mm) were found in the L3 and L6 locations, while the narrowest seeds (1.88 mm) were observed in the L12 location. Seed thickness ranged from 1.21 to 1.49 mm. The thickest seeds (1.49 mm) were found in the L1 and L7 locations, while the thinnest seeds (1.21 mm) were observed in the L4 location. It has been observed that clary sage seeds are considerably larger than those of other *Salvia* species such as *S. aegyptiaca*, *S. cabulica*, *S. coccinea*, *S. lanata*, *S.*

moorcroftiana, *S. officinalis*, *S. plebeia*, *S. reflexa*, *S. santolinifolia*, and *S. splendens*, whose seeds typically do not exceed 0.4 mm in width and length (Jabeen et al., 2023). In contrast, Tavakoli et al. (2014) reported larger seed dimensions for clary sage, with a length of 2.52 mm and a width of 2.71 mm. Similarly, Kaplan and Altundağ Çakır (2019) documented seed sizes ranging from 0.25 to 0.3 mm in length and 0.20 to 0.25 mm in width. This comparison demonstrates that the seeds analysed in the present study are generally smaller than those previously reported by Tavakoli et al. (2014) and Kaplan and Altundağ Çakır. (2019). Such differences may be attributed to genetic variation, and environmental conditions. The average characteristics of seeds collected from a different region in Türkiye were found to be similar to the results obtained in the present study (Bayram et al., 2017). On the another study, the mean seed length and width values for the studied species were as follows: *S. bracteata* (3.25 mm, 2.55 mm), *S. cadmica* (3.06 mm, 2.38 mm), *S. blepharoclæna* (2.50 mm, 1.95 mm), *S. crypthantha* (3.12 mm, 2.75 mm), *S. aethiopsis* (2.60 mm, 1.67 mm), *S. ceratophylla* (2.64 mm, 1.86 mm), *S. candidissima* subsp. *candidissima* (2.40 mm, 1.61 mm), *S. cyanescens* (2.61 mm, 1.85 mm), *S. virgata* (2.31 mm, 1.57 mm), *S. halophila* (1.77 mm, 1.14 mm), *S. verticillata* (1.88 mm, 1.14 mm), and *S. verticillata* subsp. *amasica* (2.25 mm, 1.20 mm), respectively (Özkan et al., 2009). Compared to the species studied by Özkan et al. (2009), the seed length and width values observed in our study were generally lower. In particular, seed length and width in species such as *S. bracteata*, *S. cadmica*, and *S. crypthantha* are markedly higher than the findings of the present study. However, the values observed in species such as *S. halophila*, *S. verticillata*, and *S. verticillata* subsp. *amasica* have been found to be comparable to those reported in this research.

Table 2. Some physical characteristics of clary sage seeds

Sample	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	D _g (mm)	Φ (%)	S (mm ²)	TSW (g)
L1	1.35 ^{BCD}	1.98 ^{CDE}	1.49 ^A	1.59 ^{BC}	79.87 ^{AB}	7.97 ^{BCD}	3.43 ^{AB}
L2	1.46 ^A	2.09 ^B	1.36 ^{BCD}	1.60 ^B	76.57 ^{DE}	8.12 ^B	2.79 ^C
L3	1.46 ^A	2.20 ^A	1.27 ^F	1.59 ^{BC}	72.38 ^G	8.01 ^{BC}	2.17 ^{DE}
L4	1.31 ^{CDE}	2.01 ^{CD}	1.21 ^G	1.47 ^I	73.01 ^G	6.79 ^I	2.19 ^{DE}
L5	1.30 ^{DE}	2.11 ^B	1.41 ^{BC}	1.57 ^{B-E}	74.70 ^F	7.73 ^{CDE}	3.57 ^A
L6	1.46 ^A	2.20 ^A	1.41 ^B	1.65 ^A	74.92 ^{EF}	8.68 ^A	2.61 ^{CD}
L7	1.34 ^{BCD}	1.95 ^{DEF}	1.49 ^A	1.57 ^{BCD}	80.87 ^A	7.78 ^{B-E}	2.21 ^{DE}
L8	1.39 ^{A-D}	1.93 ^{EFG}	1.30 ^{EF}	1.51 ^{GH}	78.27 ^{BC}	7.20 ^{GH}	2.96 ^{BC}
L9	1.31 ^{CDE}	1.90 ^{FG}	1.41 ^B	1.52 ^{FG}	79.98 ^A	7.26 ^{FGH}	3.08 ^{ABC}
L10	1.24 ^E	2.02 ^C	1.48 ^A	1.54 ^{D-G}	76.58 ^{DE}	7.49 ^{EFG}	2.52 ^{CD}
L11	1.34 ^{BCD}	1.97 ^{C-F}	1.36 ^{BCD}	1.53 ^{EFG}	77.85 ^{CD}	7.34 ^{FG}	2.19 ^{DE}
L12	1.13 ^F	1.88 ^G	1.35 ^{B-E}	1.42 ^J	75.74 ^{EF}	6.38 ^J	2.17 ^{DE}
L13	1.23 ^E	1.96 ^{C-F}	1.35 ^{CDE}	1.48 ^{HI}	75.54 ^{EF}	6.91 ^{HI}	1.83 ^E
L14	1.40 ^{ABC}	2.01 ^{CD}	1.37 ^{BCD}	1.57 ^{B-E}	78.00 ^{CD}	7.76 ^{B-E}	1.79 ^E
L15	1.40 ^{ABC}	2.00 ^{CDE}	1.34 ^{DE}	1.55 ^{C-F}	77.83 ^{CD}	7.59 ^{DEF}	2.86 ^C
HSD _(0.05)	0.09	0.07	0.06	0.04	1.67	0.38	0.57

D_g: Geometric mean diameter, Φ: Sphericity, S: Surface area, TSW: Thousand seed weigh. Groups not sharing the same letter are significantly different according to Tukey's HSD test (p<0.05).

On the another study, the mean seed length and width values for the studied species were as follows: *S. bracteata* (3.25 mm, 2.55 mm), *S. cadmica* (3.06 mm, 2.38 mm), *S. blepharoclæna* (2.50 mm, 1.95 mm), *S. crypthantha* (3.12 mm, 2.75 mm), *S. aethiopsis* (2.60 mm, 1.67 mm), *S. ceratophylla* (2.64 mm, 1.86 mm), *S. candidissima* subsp. *candidissima* (2.40 mm, 1.61 mm), *S. cyanescens* (2.61 mm, 1.85 mm), *S. virgata* (2.31 mm, 1.57 mm), *S. halophila* (1.77 mm, 1.14 mm), *S. verticillata* (1.88 mm, 1.14 mm), and *S. verticillata* subsp. *amasica* (2.25 mm, 1.20 mm), respectively (Özkan et al., 2009). Compared to the species studied by Özkan et al. (2009), the seed length and width values observed in our study were generally lower. In particular, seed length and width in species such as *S. bracteata*, *S. cadmica*, and *S. crypthantha* are markedly higher than the findings of the present study. However, the values observed in species such as *S. halophila*, *S. verticillata*, and *S. verticillata* subsp. *amasica* have been found to be comparable to those reported in this research. The D_g values ranged from 1.42 to 1.65 mm. The L6 location had the highest D_g value (1.65 mm), while the L12 location had the lowest value (1.42 mm). This parameter serves as a general indicator of the three-dimensional shape of the seed. In the study by Bayram et al. (2017), the value was reported as 1.97. This

indicates that the seeds analysed in our study tend to have a smaller three-dimensional shape compared to those reported by Bayram et al. (2017). The sphericity (Φ) values ranged from 72.38% to 80.87%. The L7 location had the highest sphericity value (80.87%), while the L3 location had the lowest value (72.38%). Sphericity indicates how closely the seed approximates an ideal sphere and is an important indicator of seed shape. The sphericity index was found to be similar to previous reports by Tavakoli et al. (2014) and (Bayram et al., 2017). In comparison, *Salvia hispanica* L. has been reported to have Φ values of 63–64% (Ixtaina et al., 2008) and %63-67 (Ganachari et al., 2022). These results suggest that the seeds analysed in our study are generally more spherical than those of *Salvia hispanica* L. S values ranged from 6.38 to 8.68 mm². The L6 location had the highest surface area (8.68 mm²), while the L12 location had the lowest value (6.38 mm²). Surface area is an important parameter that may affect the seed's potential for water and nutrient uptake. The surface area of the samples collected from different locations in Denizli was found to be lower than that reported in the study by Tavakoli et al. (2014) (12–14 mm²) and Bayram et al. (2017) (12.19 mm²). In comparison, *Salvia hispanica* L. has been reported to have S values of 5.42-5.79 mm² (Ixtaina et al., 2008). This comparison

highlights that the seeds in our study possess a surface area greater than *Salvia hispanica* L., but less than those found in other *Salvia* species according to previous research. TSW values ranged from 1.79 to 3.57 g. The L5 location had the highest thousand seed weight (3.57 g), while the L14 location had the lowest value (1.79 g). This parameter serves as an indicator of seed plumpness and reserve nutrient content. Tavakoli et al. (2014) reported a TSW ranging from 2 to 5 g and Bayram et al. (2017) reported a 3.4 g, which is consistent with the findings of the present study. In comparison, *Salvia hispanica* L. has been reported to have TSW values of around 1.3 g (Ganachari et al., 2022; Ixtaina et al., 2008). Taken together, these findings suggest that the TSW of the samples analysed in our study is

generally higher than that of *Salvia hispanica* L., but comparable to those reported for other *Salvia* species. The L6 location possesses the highest values in parameters of length, width, geometric mean diameter, and surface area. This indicates that the L6 location generally has the largest seeds. Although the L5 location has average seed size values, it possesses the highest TSW. This suggests that seeds from the L5 location may have greater internal plumpness and a higher endosperm content. The L7 location has the highest Φ value, indicating that the seeds from this location are closest to an ideal sphere in terms of shape. The L12 location has the lowest values for length, D_g , and S parameters. This indicates that the L12 location generally has the smallest seeds.

Figure 1. PCA biplot illustrating the relationships among physical characteristics of clary sage seeds

Principal Component 1 (PC1) and Principal Component 2 (PC2) collectively explain 72.5% of the total variance observed in the investigated characteristics, indicating that the majority of the observed variability is captured by these two components. Among the variables, L6 and L2 demonstrate high positive loadings on the first principal component

(PC1), while L3 and L1 are characterized by moderate positive loadings on PC1. D_g , S , length, L14, L15, and L5 are associated with weak positive loadings on the first principal component (PC1), suggesting that their contributions to this component are relatively minor compared to other variables. In addition, the L12 component exhibits a strong negative

loading, while L13 and L4 show moderate negative loadings on PC1. With respect to the second principal component (PC2), L1 demonstrates a moderate positive loading, whereas L9, Φ , thickness, L10, and TSW are characterized by weak positive loadings. Conversely, L3 displays a strong negative loading, L4 has a moderate negative loading, and L13, L6, and L5 width exhibit weak negative loadings, indicating varying degrees of inverse association with PC2. Analysis of the principal component analysis (PCA) (Figure 1) reveals that the altitude variable is located on the left side of the biplot, suggesting that samples collected from higher altitude regions tend to exhibit smaller seed sizes. Thickness and TSW are positioned at the top (in the positive direction) of the biplot, indicating a strong positive correlation between these variables. The observed correlation suggests that thicker seeds generally exhibit a higher thousand seed weight (TSW), implying a direct relationship between seed thickness and weight. The positioning of the width variable in the lower negative quadrant of the biplot implies a possible trade-off between seed width and thickness. Specifically, this distribution suggests that an increase in seed width is associated with a tendency for reduced seed thickness. The locations (L1–L15) are distributed and clustered in distinct areas of the biplot based on their seed traits, reflecting the variation in seed characteristics among different collection sites. The upper right region of the biplot (L1, L7) is characterized by thick, heavy, and relatively large seeds. In contrast, the lower right region (L3, L6) comprises seeds that are wide and long but relatively thin. The upper left region (L9, L10) is associated with smaller yet relatively thick seeds, while the lower left region (L4, L12, L13) includes samples collected from high-altitude locations, which are characterized by small, thin, and light seeds. L2, L5, and L14 are positioned close to the center of the biplot, suggesting that the seeds from these locations exhibit intermediate or average values for the measured traits. It can be noted that plants or seeds from L1 and L7 locations may be

considered for achieving high thousand seed weight (TSW). The L6 location stands out for producing large-sized seeds. To obtain seeds with diverse morphological characteristics, different locations can be selected accordingly. Seed size and weight are generally associated with seed quality and germination vigor. Therefore, locations situated on the right side of the biplot (particularly L1, L2, and L6) appear to have potential for the production of higher quality seeds.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the substantial geographic variation in the physical seed characteristics of clary sage within Denizli province. The observed differences in seed size, shape, and weight among locations underscore the influence of both genetic and environmental factors, particularly altitude, on seed morphology. The identification of locations such as L6, which consistently produced larger seeds, and L5, which yielded seeds with higher thousand seed weight, offers valuable insights for future breeding and selection programs aimed at improving seed quality and agronomic performance. Despite these significant findings, it should be noted that the study is limited to a single province and a single year of data collection, which may restrict the generalizability of the results to broader regions or different climatic conditions. Future research should therefore include multi-year and multi-regional studies to validate and expand upon these findings, as well as to explore the underlying genetic mechanisms responsible for the observed variation. The scientific novelty of this study lies in its detailed characterization of intraspecific seed trait diversity within a relatively understudied region, providing a valuable reference for both national and international efforts in medicinal plant breeding. The results emphasize the importance of considering local environmental conditions and genetic diversity when developing new cultivars of clary sage. By targeting locations with favorable seed traits, it is possible to enhance the efficiency of seed production, improve germination vigor, and

ultimately support the expansion of clary sage cultivation in Türkiye. These findings also highlight the potential benefits of selecting superior seed traits, such as increased yield, improved seedling establishment, and enhanced adaptability, which can contribute to the development of more resilient and productive clary sage cultivars for both medicinal and industrial applications. Furthermore, the data generated in this study provide a foundation for optimizing agricultural practices, including harvesting, processing, and storage, thereby contributing to the sustainable utilization and economic value of this important medicinal and aromatic plant.

References

- Acimovic, M.G., Loncar, B.L., Jeliaskov, V.D., Pezo, L.L., Lujic, J.P., Miljkovic, A.R., Vujisic, L.V., 2022. Comparison of volatile compounds from clary sage (*Salvia sclarea* L.) verticillasters essential oil and hydrolate. *Journal of Essential Oil-Bearing Plants*, 25(3): 555–570.
- Bayram, M., Altuntas, E., Yilar, M., 2017. Geometric, volumetric, colour and frictional properties of selected salvia species of Turkey. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 14(3): 128–135.
- Bayram, M., Yilar, M., Özgöz, E., Kadioğlu, İ., 2016. Ada çayı (*Salvia virgata* Jacq.) tohumlarının bazı fiziksel özelliklerinin belirlenmesi. *Nevşehir Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, 5: 325–325.
- Cui, H., Zhang, X., Zhou, H., Zhao, C., Lin, L., 2015. Antimicrobial activity and mechanisms of *Salvia sclarea* essential oil. *Botanical Studies*, 56: 16.
- Brown, B., Aaron, M., 2001. The politics of nature. In: J. Smith (Ed), *The Rise of Modern Genomics*, 3rd edn., Wiley, New York, pp. 230-257.
- Dumanoğlu, Z., Özkan, Ş.S., Demiroğlu Topçu, G., 2019. İtalyan çimi (*Lolium multiflorum* L.) çeşitlerine ait tohumların bazı fiziksel özelliklerinin belirlenmesi. *Uluslararası Tarım ve Yaban Hayatı Bilimleri Dergisi*, 5(2): 292–298.
- Ganachari, A., Patil, P.A., Reddy, M., Khan, H., Bhoopal Reddy, S. 2022. Physical properties of Chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) seeds required for the design of equipment. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(3): 2253–2256.
- Gonciareuc, M., Balmuş, Z., 2010. Performant new varieties of *Salvia sclarea* L. with different period of vegetation carried out in the republic of Moldova. *Ştiinţele Naturii*, 26(1): 9–13.
- González-Gallegos, J.G., Bedolla-García, B.Y., Cornejo-Tenorio, G., Fernández-Alonso, J.L., Fragoso-Martínez, I., García-Peña, M.D.R., Harley, R.M., Klitgaard, B., Martínez-Gordillo, M.J., Wood, J.R.I., Zamudio, S., Zona, S., Xifreda, C.C., 2020. Richness and distribution of *Salvia* subg. *Calosphaea* (Lamiaceae). *International Journal of Plant Sciences*, 181(8): 831–856.
- Grigoriadou, K., Trikkas, F.A., Tsoktouridis, G., Krigas, N., Sarropoulou, V., Papanastasi, K., Maloupa, E., Makris, A.M., 2020. Micropropagation and cultivation of *Salvia sclarea* for essential oil and sclareol production in northern Greece. *In Vitro Cellular and Developmental Biology-Plant*, 56(1): 51–59.
- Ixtaina, V.Y., Nolasco, S.M., Tomás, M.C., 2008. Physical properties of chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) seeds. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 28(3): 286–293.
- Jabeen, S., Zafar, M., Ahmad, M., Althobaiti, A.T., Ozdemir, F.A., Kutlu, M.A., Makhkamov, T.K., Sultana, S., Ameen, M., Majeed, S., 2023. Ultra-sculpturing of seed morphotypes in selected species of genus *Salvia* L. and their taxonomic significance. *Plant Biology*, 25(1): 96–106.

- Kaplan, F., Altundağ Ç., 2019. Morphological characteristics of some *Salvia* L. taxa in Sakarya province (Turkey). *Eurasian Journal of Forest Science*, 7(2): 133–144.
- Karik, Ü., Çinar, O., Tunçtürk, M., Şekeroğlu, N., Gezici, S., 2018. Essential oil composition of some sage (*Salvia* spp.) species cultivated in İzmir (Turkey) ecological conditions. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 52(4): 102–107.
- Özkan, M., Aktas Z.K., Özdemir, C., Guerin, G., 2009. Nutlet morphology and its taxonomic utility in *Salvia* (Lamiaceae: Mentheae) from Turkey. *Acta Botanica Croatica*, 68(1): 105–115.
- Safaei-Ghomi, J., Masoomi, R., Jookar Kashi, F., Batooli, H., 2016. Bioactivity of the essential oil and methanol extracts of flowers and leaves of *Salvia sclarea* L. from central Iran. *Journal of Essential Oil-Bearing Plants*, 19(4): 885–896.
- Sharopov, F.S., Setzer, W.N., 2012. The essential oil of *Salvia sclarea* L. from Tajikistan. *Records of Natural Products*, 6(1): 75-79.
- Tavakoli, M., Naghdi Badi, H., Rafiee, H., Labbafi, M.R., Ghorbani Nohooji, M., Zand, E., Mehrafarin, A., 2014. Physico-chemical properties of seeds in valuable medicinal species of the genus *Salvia* L. *Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 13(51): 71–83.
- Tursun, A.O., Sipahioglu, H.M., Telci, I., 2021. Genetic relationships and diversity within cultivated accessions of *Salvia officinalis* L. in Turkey. *Plant Biotechnology Reports*, 15(5): 663–672.

To Cite

Uskutoğlu, T., 2025. Physical Seed Characteristics of Clary Sage (*Salvia sclarea* L.) at Different Altitudes in Denizli. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(3): 787-795.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15848367>.